

PROSPECTS OF MODERN CIVILIZATION

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Abstract: The article comments on the characteristics and prospective aspects of modern civilization. Views related to the influence of modern civilization on the life of man and society are analyzed.

Key words: civilization, modern society, technical revolution, technocracy, liberalization, culture. The terminological meaning of the concept of civilization is quite different from its dictionary meaning.

Nowadays, the concept of civilization is used in many senses: -

- as a synonym of the concept of "culture" (F. Schelling).
- As an antipad of culture (N. Berdiyayev, N. Roerich).
- Weakening of culture, stages of its birth and death (O. Spengler).
- Concrete historical type of society.
- As a religious unit.
- To express the history of technological development of society.

Since the 18th century, thanks to the French enlighteners, the term civilization has become widespread in science. The Enlightenment interpreted civilization as a society based on reason and justice, and used civilization as a synonym for the concept of culture. This tradition is accepted by many people. Especially in journalistic literature, they are often used as synonyms. Scientists who wrote about civilization, especially the Italian Gian Battista Vico (17th-18th century), civilizations are born, reach the peak of development, then gradually begin to fade and die, according to his shows three periods in his life. This is a consequence of looking at the concept of civilization as a social organism. Human society is a truly integrated social organism. Civilization is a closed discrete form of its development.

In essence, civilization means the level of material and spiritual development of society. In this, all areas, directions, layers, parts, material and spiritual life, social existence and social consciousness, ideology are considered as a single system. Spirituality in a broad sense is the main criterion for distinguishing civilizations that lived at the same time. Civilization is a form of existence and development of society [2;81].

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The modern period of the development of society is determined by the development of man-made civilization. This type originated in the European region, but is practiced in various versions both in the West and in the East, where traditional societies collide. The most important feature is rapid scientific and technical progress, which turns man-made civilization into an extremely dynamic society. Currently, a new stage of the scientific and technical revolution, which began in the early 70s and 80s of the 20th century and opens up unlimited prospects for the further development of the productive forces of society and the enrichment of its spiritual life, is rapidly developing. Microelectronics, informatics, robotics, biotechnology, creation of materials with predetermined properties, nanotechnologies, atomic energy, aerospace industry and others are among the leading, priority directions.

The new stage of development of the scientific and technical revolution should correspond to the new stage of the social situation of the society. In the future society, the tasks of acquiring new knowledge, assimilating it in the process of continuous education, and its technological and human application prevail.

The values of man-made civilization are formed historically. Their conditions are the achievements of the culture of antiquity and the European Middle Ages, which developed during the Reformation and Enlightenment. Man is an active being, in active relationship with the world.

The main idea is the transformation of the world and the subjugation of nature by man. Transformative activity is the main purpose of man. The ideals of man-made civilization are the ability of the sovereign individual to freely join the most diverse social communities and corporations. Power and domination in this system of relations includes ownership and appropriation of the results of activity in the form of goods.

At the root of the crisis of modern civilization lies the conflict between the growing needs of society and the ability of the natural environment to meet them. This contradiction cannot be overcome. Without solving this contradiction, the transition of world civilization to sustainable development is

impossible. It is precisely today that the problems and prospects of modern civilization are gaining special meaning due to the fact that the contradictions and problems of the global order are becoming more and more acute.

Cosmogenic civilization was based on tools and manual technology, and was characterized by a great dependence of society on natural forces, in which the cosmos of the world determines the meaning of life, defines laws, fixed forms of social organization, and the relationship of individuals with social institutions.

Man-made civilization: machine technology, extensive development of science and its gradual transformation into a direct productive force, wage labor, market relations, a high level of professional culture in all its forms. Overcoming the crisis, which has affected all countries and regions of the world community in different degrees and in different forms, can be ensured only by transitioning to a new, higher, more efficient and less wasteful way of reproduction of society itself.

The material basis of this began to form along with the development of information technologies, which form the content of a new type of civilization - the process of information formation. The source of development is not the external conditions of human life, but it itself. Scientific and informational resources, level of socio-political consciousness, moral criteria, spiritual-cultural relations and other elements of spiritual life, which determine the nature of reproduction technology and social development of the whole society, become important.

The formation and development of information civilization has become a global process. The developing human civilization based on information technology is a society of social justice, for which there is currently no alternative. Social justice is one of the universal general sociological and moral principles of organizing social life.

Modern philosophy sees social justice as the essence of the information society, which will replace the industrial civilization. Its aspects are as follows: the presence of a regulated market with a diversified economy and the leading role of the public sector; labor base, paying employees according to the quantity and quality of work, strong social protection of the layers of the society who cannot work for certain reasons; forms of democratic organization in all spheres of public life; state management of all socially important processes; high level of science and culture, especially legal and spiritual.

A society of social justice is a civil society that determines the status of a person based on the quantity and quality of work. It is characterized by higher

indicators in socio-economic, political and spiritual spheres compared to capitalism and socialism. The change of civilizations is the continuation of life in new socio-cultural conditions. During the evolution of socio-cultural factors of life, civilization ensures not only the continuity of the social process, but also its continuity.

In the course of its development, civilization forms a mechanism for maintaining unity between the past, present and future. The processes of global integration, the growing scale of interaction between economic, ethno-national, political and other subjects of social action bring modern civilization to a new stage of human development.

The urgency of the problems of modern humanity is that civilization is capable not only of destroying itself, but also of destroying all the splendor of life. Currently, many philosophers, sociologists and historians tend to think that at the current stage of human development, a single civilization is being formed on the whole planet. The acceleration of this idea in science and public consciousness helped to become aware of the globalization of social and cultural processes in the modern world.

Globalization is primarily related to the internationalization of all social activities on Earth. This internationalization means that the entire humanity is included in a single socio-cultural, economic, political and other system of connections, interactions and relations. Thus, in the modern era, compared to past historical periods, the planetary unity of humanity has increased immeasurably, a radically new supersystem associated with a common destiny and common responsibility.

Therefore, scientists and philosophers consider it legitimate to talk about the formation of a single civilization and the need for a new planetary way of thinking. Such a globalist approach is clearly visible in the concepts of "post-industrial society" and "technological era" of American sociologists D. Bell, Z. Brzezinski, A. Toffler and others.

These concepts focus on the fact that each technological revolution leads to profound changes not only in the productive forces of society, but also in the entire way of life of people. A characteristic feature of the modern technological revolution associated with public information is that it creates radically new conditions for the universalization and globalization of human interaction. Thanks to the wide development of mass media and communications, the deepening of the division of labor and specialization, humanity has united into a single socio-cultural unity.

the existence of such unity sets its demands on the whole of humanity and on the individual. The higher the level of technical production and the entire human activity, the higher should be the interaction between the person himself and the environment, therefore, new requirements for the individual: he must be highly skilled, a virtuoso of technology must be skillfully combined. , ultimate competence in their specialty with social responsibility and ethical universal values.

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The specific analysis of each of them is within the competence of special sciences: sociology, demography, etc. Philosophers, on the other hand, focus on issues of ideological meaning, considering these issues from the point of view of the possibilities and prospects of human existence. In this aspect, the ecological problem comes first.

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